



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, male holotype, left pedipalp chela, external



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, male holotype, left pedipalp patella, external



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, male holotype, left pedipalp patella, ventral



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature female paratype, dorsal



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature female paratype, ventral



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature female paratype, right pedipalp chela and movable finger



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature female paratype, left pedipalp chela and movable finger



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature male paratype, dorsal



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature male paratype, ventral



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature male paratype, right pedipalp chela and movable finger



*Scorpiops deshpandei*, immature male paratype, left pedipalp chela and movable finger



*Scorpions kovariki*, female holotype, right pedipalp chela, external



*Scorpions kovariki*, female holotype, right pedipalp patella, external



*Scorpions kovariki*, female holotype, right pedipalp patella, ventral



*Scorpions jendeki*, series 1 (75% ethanol-preserved); stacked photo



*Scorpions jendeki*, series 2 (dry-preserved and live) and *Scorpions kovariki*, single shot



*Scorpiops jendeki*, carapacial anteromedian notch and ocular tubercle (S, series)



*Scorpiops kovariki*, female holotype, carapacial anteromedian notch and ocular tubercle



Female *S. jendeki* and *S. kovariki*, photographed with mobile phone



Examined movable fingers of *Scorpions jendeki*



Additional materials of *Scorpiops jendeki* (3 males, 2 females) collected from Lianghe, Yunnan



Adult female *Scorpiops jendeki* used for DNA sequencing



Chela comparison between examined *S. jendeki* (except for the one used for sequencing) and *S. kovarki*



Chela comparison between adult female *S. jendeki* and *S. kovarki* under UV light



Three additional adults of *S. jendeki* (not examined in detail)



*Scorpions rufus*, female paratype (Lv & Di, 2023: figs. 32–33)



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female holotype, left pedipalp chela, external



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female holotype, left pedipalp patella, external



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female holotype, left pedipalp patella, ventral



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female holotype, right pedipalp chela, dorsal, UV



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female holotype, right pedipalp chela, external, UV



*Scorpions matthewi*, female holotype *in vivo*, photos taken with mobile phone



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratypes in vivo (Nos. 1–3), photographed by Tongtong



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 1 (PTC 4/4, PVTC 7/7), photographed by Tongtong



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 2 (PTC 4/4, PVTC 6/7), photographed by Tongtong



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 3 (PTC 5/5, PVTC 7/7), photographed by Tongtong



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 1, left chela (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female paratype No. 1, right chela (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female PT No. 1, left & right movable finger & patella (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 2, left chela (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpions matthewi*, female paratype No. 2, right chela (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpiops matthewi*, female PT No. 2, left & right movable finger & patella (examined by V. Tang)



*Scorpions songi*, adult male, dry preserved



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, carapacial anteromedian notch



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, left pedipalp chela, external



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, left pedipalp movable finger



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, pectines



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, right pedipalp patella, ventral



*Scorpiops songi*, adult male, left pedipalp patella, ventral